

THE BRAND DNA PROCESS: HOW BRANDING CAN TRIGGER EMOTIONAL RESPONSES.

NEUROSCIENCE KNOWLEDGE APPLIED IN BRANDING FAVELA FASHION

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ABSTRACT

The general objective of this work is to present the Brand DNA Process, and, specifically, to expose how this methodology can diagnose an organization's deeper emotional adjectives to be transmitted in branding strategies, so it can develop an identity to which consumers respond emotionally. As will be outlined, neuroscience research demonstrates that the emotional brain can be decisive in buying decisions. In order to create branding strategies that target this emotional brain, the Brand DNA Process was applied in the case study Branding Favela Fashion, thus developing an emotional appeal for collective's brand. This methodology resulted in the creation of a design tool that transmits the organization's deeper personality, which enhanced the brand's emotional allure and its relationship with consumers.

Keywords: design, branding, Brand DNA, neuroscience, emotional brain.

INTRODUCTION

BRAND IDENTITY

Many times the image consumers have of a brand is not the same as the identity it wishes to transmit. By investing in brand identity, the brand strengthens, and the image begins to mirror the identity. Consumers begin to recognize the brand, its attributes, and its promises, eventually building a relationship of loyalty with emotional attachment. While difficult to depict in elaborate detail, this identity is manifest through the five senses: through graphical images and sound, and

potentially touch, smell, and taste, creating all together an opportunity for a multi-faceted personality.

Certain brands, territories, or organizations may have a signature manner of communicating or may have an established image stemming from consumer perspective, yet completely ignore how they define their identity. A brand must be conscious of its identity in order to sustain and build upon it.

Branding makes a promise of the brand experience, how to live the brand. The means by which this promise reaches the client becomes part of the strategy used by the organization (Gomez and Olhats, 2010). This strategy is constructed from a vision, emerges from the values and culture of the company, is in line with the marketing strategy, and reflects a deep comprehension of the needs and perceptions of the consumer (Wheeler, 2008). "As the dominant form of communication, there is more to branding than advertising. This is because people seek a physical and sensory manifestation of a concept. Design is an emotional vocabulary that transcends words. It not only connects with consumers but also becomes the only brand language that matters" (Gobé, 2010, p. 114). It is also through branding that graphic designers create promise of value. "This area of design aims at conceiving complex systems of visual identity that fit with the company's internal systems of signage and communications. In its external communications, the company differentiates itself by a specific graphic and verbal language and applies these messages according to its different publics" (Borja de Mozota, 2003, p. 8).

But above all, it is through branding that the relationship between the brand and the consumer is forged. "The nature of these relationships can vary, and these bonds help us to understand some of the possible meanings products have for us" (Solomon, 2010, p. 37). Self-concept attachment, nostalgic attachment, interdependence, or love, are some of the types of relationships a consumer can forge with a product (Solomon, 2010). Beyond a visual identity that the consumer can recognize, successful brands "connect with their consumers not simply by meeting their rational needs, but by addressing the emotional context of the need, as well" (Kathman, 2010, p. 107).

Once there is an emotional bond between the consumer and the brand, the user identifies himself with the brand, creating a means of personal association of self image manifest through internal reflection and outward projection (Kathman, 2010). Further developing on this emotional bond, Tom Peters (2009), author of *Re-imagine!*, states, "Branding is ultimately about nothing more (and nothing less) than heart. It's about passion...what you care about. It's about what's inside - what's inside you, what's inside your company." It is a language of feeling and sentiments, which, in a world of excess information and scarcity of time, is more valued than information (Neumeier, 2008). Marc Gobé (2010, p. 109) creates an analogy where "design is to branding what jazz is to music: a new language of wonderful emotional experiences that unites brands with audiences. Design humanizes brands, stimulating our senses and feelings, and celebrates the power of collaboration and improvisation."

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

BRANDING

According to Kotler (*apud* Tybout and Calkins, 2006), "branding is much more than naming an offer. It means making a promise to customers about how to live an experience in a complete performance level, i.e., it means 'to live the brand'." In accordance with Gobé (2010), "brands must be connected with the culture and reach people's hearts." Therefore, branding is more than just making sure that customers recognize a logo or the name of a product, it means creating an emotional association between the client

and the product, service or business: "brands must change from 'communications' and 'commodities' to *excitement* and *inspiration*."

The purpose of branding, according to Healey (2009), "is to reinforce a good reputation, encourage loyalty, ensure quality, convey a perception of greater value to ensure a sense of affirmation and entry into an imagined community of shared values." The strategies of branding, then, are focused, according to Roberts (2004), in "making people feel good about the brand, to get a positive emotion."

In branding, we have increasingly heard about creating an emotional bond between brand and consumers, while, according to Gobé (2002, p. 18) "the intangible values became more valuable than the tangible". Then, brands start to carry deep currents of meanings in terms of context of use, socio-philosophical nature of consumers and of cultures to which they belong (Batey, 2010). Since, according to Valentine (1995 *apud* Batey, 2010, p.15), "we understand the world and its meanings through cultural premises, systems of shared meanings and values and beliefs we accept as natural and appreciated", a brand communicates with consumers at the level of senses and emotions, a brand becomes alive for people, by forging a deep and lasting connection (Gobé, 200, p. 19).

In this sense, "what is sold out is not a product, but a vision, a concept, a lifestyle associated with the brand": an emotion (Lipovetsky, 2007, p. 40). According to Gobé (2002, p. 11), few companies know the art of achieving, with intelligence and sensitivity, the true force behind human emotions. The emotional branding provides credibility and personality to a brand, strongly connecting it with people on personal and holistic levels. The creation of emotional brands is based in that exclusive confidence established with the public: "to create brands not only refers to omnipresence, visibility and functions, but also to the emotional connection with people in their everyday life. It is only when a product or a service causes an emotional dialogue with consumers, that it can really be qualified as a brand" (Desgrippes *apud* Gobé, 2002, p. 17).

The brand focuses on the stronger aspect of human character; the desire to transcend the material satisfaction and experience the emotional fulfillment (Gobé, 2002; p. 19). For this to be accomplished, it is necessary to understand how a consumer's emotions influence the relationship between consumer and product. In this regard, the studies in neuroscience contribute to branding, providing a deeper knowledge about the human emotional brain, and how it affects relationships with brands.

THE EMOTIONAL BRAIN

The consumer response to a stimulus, such as the visual perception of a product, "is determined by two distinct styles of information processing: the cognitive and the preferential". In other words, images, for example, "imply a cognitive treatment of them (a process of thinking) and/or an emotional treatment of the information (a process of feeling)". Therefore, information processing is either logical, rational, sequential, or holistic and synthetic (Borja de Mozota, 2011, p. 112).

In this sense, Rodrigues (2011, p. 84) explains that when we make a decision we can make it through a long process of deliberation of various options, considering the pros and cons before choosing the most logical solution. In this case, the decision-making seems to be a rational decision, an intentional process based on the language. However, many times, decision making can be a different phenomenon, very intuitive, which involves simply choosing the option that we "feel" it is more correct. In the latter case, the decision appears to be based on something quite different than reflection, more visceral, more emotional, which arises spontaneously in the form of preference.

Thus, there are two mental systems that lead to assessment: one that performs extensive reflections, but consumes more time and mental resources; and a more automatic, but very imprecise one. "Besides being anatomically distinct mental systems, the different processing speed is the feature that most distinguishes them" (Ledoux and Lieberman, 2007 *apud* Rodrigues, 2001, p 84).

"These two fundamentally different ways of knowing interact to construct our mental life. One, the rational mind, is the way of understanding that we typically are aware: most prominent in the field of attention, thoughtful, able to ponder and reflect. But besides this there is another mental knowledge system: impulsive and powerful, though sometimes illogical – the emotional mind". These two minds, the emotional and the rational, most often work in perfect harmony, combining their two different ways of knowing to guide us through the world. Typically, there is a balance between them, in which emotion is fed while informs the operations of the rational mind, and this one refines and sometimes interposes the contributions of emotion. However, the emotional and rational minds are semi-independent faculties, reflecting each of them, the functioning of distinct, but interconnected circuits inside the brain (Goleman, 2009, p. 31).

In the human brain, the emotional mind is related to the amygdala: from the Greek word for 'almond', it is a group of interconnected almond-shaped structures perched above the brainstem, near the bottom edge of the limbic system. There are two amygdalae, one on each side of the head (Goleman, 2009, p. 36). Joseph LeDoux (*apud* Goleman, 2009, p. 37), neuroscientist from the Center of Neuroscience at the University of New York, explains through his research how the amygdalae can take control of what we do, while the thinking brain, the neocortex, is still striving to reach a decision.

The investigations of LeDoux (*apud* Goleman, 2009, p. 39) demonstrated that the sensory systems from the eyes and ears reach the brain passing first through the thalamus and then – through a simple synapse – through the amygdala; a second signal from the thalamus is sent to the neocortex, the thinking brain. "This branching allows the amygdala to begin to respond before the neocortex, which analyzes the information, making it pass through several levels of brain circuits, before understanding it completely and then formulating its own answer".

A visual system flows first from the retina to thalamus, where it is translated into brain language. Most of the message then goes to the visual cortex, where it is analyzed and evaluated in terms of meaning and

Figure 01. Some Important Cerebral Structures. Source: <http://www.quora.com/Philosophy/Is-there-such-a-thing-as-the-subconscious>

appropriate response; if that response is emotional, a signal goes to the amygdala, which triggers the emotional centers. But a small part of the signal goes directly from the thalamus to the amygdala in a quicker transmission, allowing a faster response (although less accurate). Thereby, the amygdala can trigger an emotional response before the cortical centers have had time to fully understand what is happening (Goleman, 2009, p. 40).

This direct route has a huge advantage in terms of brain time, which is counted in milliseconds. The amygdala of a rat is able to begin responding to a perception in only twelve milliseconds. The route thalamus-neocortex-amygdala takes approximately twice as long. According to Goleman (2009, p. 45) “equivalent measurements in regards to the human brain have still not been made, but it is believed that the relation will probably be the same”.

According to the author, the route of emergency from eyes or ears to thalamus and amygdala is crucial: saves time in an emergency. And also offers an extremely fast way of linking the emotions, resulting in feeling before thinking. “No wonder we understand so little about our more violent emotions [...]: these emotions are triggered independently, and before, thought” (Goleman, 2009, p. 45). This demonstrates that visual stimuli are capable of activating a surprisingly large number of brain regions without coming into conscious awareness (Aamodt and Wang, 2009, p. 227).

Although the amygdala is known for its role in fear responses, it also quickly reacts to positive emotional stimuli, such as the logo of our favorite brand stamped on a product. “Altogether, the amygdala seems to be important to concentrate on events with emotional significance in the world around us”. The neurons in amygdalae respond to vision, hearing, or touch, and sometimes, these three senses at once. “Many of these neurons have preference for certain objects, especially gratifying objects” (Aamodt and Wang, 2009, p. 138).

When we see a product, “we realize not only what it is in the first milliseconds, but also decide whether we like it or not. The ‘cognitive unconscious’ presents to our awareness not only the identity of what we see, but also an opinion about it”. In other words, our emotions have a mind of their own, able to provide ‘views’ independently of our rational mind (Goleman, 2009, p. 41).

However, “while the amigdala works triggering an anxiety and impulsive reaction, the area of the neocortical brain gives a more analytical and appropriate response to our emotional impulses. The neocortical response is slower than the emergency mechanism because it involves more circuits”. Normally, the prefrontal areas regulate our emotional reactions from the beginning. “The highest projection of sensory information that leaves the thalamus

doesn't go to amygdala, but to the neocortex, and its many centers responsible for recording and deciphering what is being perceived". This information, and our response, is coordinated by the prefrontal lobes, the center of planned and organized actions in view of a goal" (Goleman, 2009, p. 46-47).

"Thus, in a certain sense, we have two brains, two minds, and two different types of intelligence: rational and emotional" (Goleman, 2009, p. 50), that Rodrigues (2011, p. 84) called automatic and deliberative: "the automatic system produces fast reactions, but inaccurate assessments for the decision; while the deliberative system produces thinner decisions, but with higher cost of time and mental energy. The final product of this automatic system will be the emotional response, involuntary and adaptive (Ledoux, 1994; Damásio, 1994 *apud* Rodrigues, 2011, p. 84).

Then, we may prefer/choose, i.e. decide, on a non-conscious way (not rational). All these studies suggest the existence of an emotional/affective automatic and preconscious processing (Rodrigues, 2011, p. 90). Although the meaning of the expression 'automatic' is up for debate, most of researchers use this term to indicate the processing that occurs below the threshold of consciousness (Ledoux, 2000 *apud* Rodrigues, 2011, p. 88).

This information is valuable to branding. "The decision between buying or not is primarily a physical-chemical, biological process that occurs inside the brain, and not outside" (Camargo, 2010, p. 164). This means that most brands should have a strong emotional appeal that may trigger an emotional preconscious decision, which can reflect in preference, and even in a buying decision. At this point, developing a Brand DNA is valuable, to diagnose the basic emotional adjectives of a brand, so they can be transmitted to its consumers.

METHOD

BRAND DNA PROCESS

A brand is a living entity that is born from a vision and grows by building relationships. A brand must be cared for in order to maintain an emotional

relationship with its consumers, and its personality should be able to radiate through its products and communication, not only in the marketing department, but throughout the entire organization. Similar to living organisms then, a brand also has a series of intrinsic traits defined by its DNA, with which consumers can identify, and from which can arise an emotional relationship. "For brands to be able to connect with human beings, brands need to develop an authentic DNA that is the core of their true differentiation", and that can trigger a consumer's preconscious emotional response in the form of preference among other brands. "This DNA will reflect the brand's identity in consumers' social networks. Brands with unique DNAs will have their characters built up through their lives" (Kotler, 2010, p. 34).

Brand DNA focuses on brand personality, and building identity from the inside. As Kapferer (2009, p. 122) claims, "identity is not something that can be bolted on: it is nurtured from the brand roots, its heritage, everything that gives its unique authority and legitimacy in a specific territory of values and benefits. It translates to its DNA, the genes of the brand", which by transmitting an identity, like a living being, awakens an emotional response in consumers, through the preconscious amygdala reaction. Once the consumer identifies with the brand personality, the response from his emotional brain will be positive.

In order to decipher this Brand DNA, inherent to each brand, although possibly not fully evident, the methodology, Brand DNA Process, can be employed. In its essence, the Brand DNA Process, developed by Gomez (2009), provides a guide to determining this DNA. Through evaluation activities with the company's stakeholders, the organization can explicitly verify the genetic characteristics that the brand holds (Gomez, 2009). This application can occur during the three stages of a brand's lifecycle: planning, evaluation, or restructuring.

The Brand DNA consists of four key words, like the four components of the human DNA – adenine, cytosine, guanine, and thymine – and one integrating concept that unites these four, like the hydrogen bonds that link the nucleotides.

Figure 02. The brand DNA.

In the Brand DNA Process, the five concepts of the Brand DNA are memes, the genetic code of the organization. Meme, according to Dawkins (2003), “is the cultural counterpart of the gene, a unit of information that passes from person to person, from generation to generation, by means that are not genetic, but by imitation”. Making a metaphorical analogy, it can be said that living beings have a genetic code, and the ‘non-living beings’ (ideas, objects, corporations, etc) have a memetic code.

“Meme is an idea, the kind of complex idea which constitutes a specific and memorable unit. This idea is propagated by vehicles that are the physical manifestations of the meme” (Dennett *apud* Brodie, 2010, p. 30). The five adjectives of the Brand DNA are memes that are propagated in the brand activities from insiders to consumers, like emotional triggers that activate the amygdala preconscious response.

One of the key characteristics of the methodology of the Brand DNA Process is the manner in which it creates a dialogue between the designers and stakeholders of the company. In order for the Brand DNA to be truly genuine to the brand’s personality, it must be constructed from within, with orientation of the design team. First, the brand needs a positive emotional response from those responsible for the brand’s identity, so they can transmit the adequate

Brand DNA to their consumers. The Brand DNA can be transported from one individual to another through forms of communication, where the memes are transferred from one mind to another, like an emotional virus.

As more than a simple consultation or diagnostic, the Brand DNA Process aims to create a ‘mind virus’ - “something that exists and infect people with memes” (Brodie, 2010, p. 37) – to transmit an emotional appeal and trigger preference reactions in human minds. Thereunto, it integrates company opinion makers, stakeholders involved in some manner with the brand (customers, partners, family members, etc.) and designers. By involving these stakeholders, in the design process, they become part of the process, which gives them a certain ownership over the ideas generated (Ambrose and Harris, 2011). By constructing or validating the DNA from within, the stakeholders and those who represent the brand gain better results when thinking, speaking, and acting for the brand, creating the type of emotional experience only successful brands can deliver (Schultz in: Tybout and Calkins, 2006), transmitting the concepts of the brand DNA as memes, that will work as emotional triggers in the consumers emotional brain. In order to become passionate defenders of the brand and generate a positive preconscious response from consumer’s amygdala, all those involved with it must understand the brand, how it is constructed, organized, and the promises it vows to make (Schultz in: Tybout and Calkins, 2006).

The methodology consists of eight steps, which have been developed through an analysis of tools used in design, marketing, business, and parallel disciplines. These steps engage the designer in the process by allowing him to understand the current context and future goals of the organization.

CASE STUDY

BRANDING FAVELA FASHION

To explore the development and impact of the Brand DNA Process, this methodology was applied on the collective Costurando Ideais, based in the Santa Marta *favela* in Rio de Janeiro.

Brand DNA Process

Brand DNA Tool

Figure 03. The Brand DNA Process.

Defining '*favela*' is a subject of debate considering that its definition is dependent upon the social position of the person or group defining it (Burgos, 2009). The commonly accepted political definition of *favela* is often similar to the United Nations Human Settlements Programme definition of a slum ('*favela*' being the direct translation of 'slum' in Brazilian Portuguese). The 2003 Global Report on Human Settlements states that a slum is "a contiguous settlement where the inhabitants are characterized as having inadequate housing and basic services. A slum is often not recognized and addressed by the public authorities as an integral or equal part of the city" (UN-Habitat, 2002c *apud* UN-Habitat, 2003).

While every brand is capable of discovering its DNA, experience in the *favela* has demonstrated expressively strong emotions from projects built from within the communities. *Favelas* are composed of communities with strong interpersonal bonds, great pride in their endeavors, and an urge for expression. These emotions and the relentless eagerness for creative expression present in *favelas* incited the search for a project wishing to develop its brand identity in this setting. In an environment where

uncertainty, crisis, and chaos have always been abundant, a culture of creativity developed to escape from this very situation. While things are ameliorating in the *favelas*, through pacification programs, this strive for creativity and emotional expression continues. By using design methodologies to capture this emotion and transform it into a tool, individual or collective endeavors on behalf of community members can be strengthened. Furthermore, since Brand DNA's premise is to work with brand identity based on its emotional ties and personality, applying the methodology in the *favela* was evermore pertinent.

The collective, Costurando Ideais, formed in 2000 through a common urge of women wishing to gather funds to purchase sewing machines and other material to create garments. By uniting, these women of the community, were able to acquire a locale to work, the necessary material to begin their projects, and their first clients. The collective was founded and continues to work on the steep hill on which this *favela* rests and has performed fashion shows in the community's samba school and arena. The collective's principal objective is to provide an atelier where women of the community can work together

creating garments and accessories. They produce bags, jewelry, and clothing made of diverse recycled materials and work with techniques such as crochet and embroidery to embellish their work. Yet they lack knowledge of the advantages of design and branding in creating a successful brand that can reach the consumer's emotional brain. This lack has led to an unclear brand identity, reluctance to plan collections, decreased motivation in the corporate culture, and thus unattractiveness for the consumer. A bit more than ten years has passed, yet the group's way of working has not changed, and its ability to attract and maintain an emotional relationship with customers remains a struggle.

The problem that guided this research through this case study is Costurando Ideais' lack of a strong and strategic brand identity, impeding its communication, commercialization, and credibility. Without that, the organization has not been able to create an emotional appeal.

In order to aid this collective define its path, the Brand DNA Process was applied by interviewing opinion makers and analyzing data. The core phase of the Brand DNA Process, is the Creative Event, where the designer and stakeholders of the organization come together to establish the brand's DNA. The Creative Event applies the Brand DNA Tool in a relaxed and creative environment. It is a reunion with the organization's stakeholders (internal and external actors with an interest or concern in the brand), to apply the Brand DNA Tool, a tool composed of multiple emotional brainstorming sessions and results in a debate to establish the core adjectives of the Brand DNA. Through lengthy debate of each suggested word, determining if each word is actually emotionally differential and unique to this collective, and if it can be considered as one of the five main characteristics or personality traits of the brand, the final adjectives were defined.

The adjectives chosen were:

- Criador (Creator)
- Maravilhoso (Marvelous)
- Colorido (Colorful)
- Autêntico (Authentic)

- Irreverente (Irreverent)

"Criador" represented the talent and innovation inherent to the collective and added an element addressing how the collective creates ideals for *favela* residents. It also creates talent by teaching its members the skills necessary to sew or broider. "Maravilhoso", meaning marvelous, described the collective's traits of creating pretty and joyful pieces. Since Rio de Janeiro is often dubbed "A Cidade Maravilhosa" this word was all the more pertinent. The adjective "colorido" is also reminiscent of the word joy, but in addition refers to the colored fabrics used in many of Costurando Ideais' designs. Authentic referred to the collective's location and spirit. Proud to be from the *favela*, the members choose to embrace this characteristic in their designs and way of working, accepting the participation of any community member. Irreverent described the attitude the collective has, in choosing not to follow consumer trends as defined by *o asfalto* (literally "the asphalt" referring to outside the *favela*). Their work is true to their heart, as they move to the beat of their own drum. Lastly, "criador" was chosen as the integrating concept – the concept from which all others stem. While these traits were already present, the Brand DNA Process enabled the collective to unveil this deeply rooted Brand DNA.

As a combination these words are unique to Costurando Ideais. They define the essence of the collective's activity, its mentality, and its personality. All together, these adjectives transmit the organization's emotions in all its activities, as memes, creating an emotional relationship with the insiders and with its consumers. When they identify with these memes, they emotionally respond in form of preference. Since the human emotional intelligence is dynamic and 'learns' throughout life (Pink, 2009), memes can influence decisions, whether they are simple or complex. This influence caused by memes can be either positive or negative depending on how it is 'sold' or absorbed by the consumers. In the Brand DNA case, the consumer responds positively when he emotionally identifies with the memes.

In order to graphically represent the Brand DNA established, a mood board enables a visualization of the concepts present in the company's genome

CONCLUSION

Each brand is unique in its personality and values. Its Brand DNA demonstrates its deepest emotional attributes and aids in the construction of a strong brand identity, by which the brand can trigger an emotional preconscious preference in its consumers. Since, as proven by neuroscience studies, the emotional brain has an important, and sometimes decisive, role in brand preference, organizations must be able to decipher and transmit these emotional attributes. The Brand DNA revealed through applying the Brand DNA Process in the collective Costurando Ideais is unique to this organization. By applying the DNA adjectives in its branding strategies, transmitting its five concepts as memes that work as emotional triggers in the human mind, the brand is creating an emotional bond with its consumers, using knowledge of neuroscience and its influence of the emotional brain in preferences and decisions. This bond with the consumer can be accredited to the increased internal emotional attachment to the collective demonstrated through greater involvement in events and fairs. This in turn has increased sales and the attraction of new consumers subsequent to the application of the Brand DNA Process. Applying the recommendations, developed from analysis of the data gathered during the Brand DNA Process, the collective is creating order out of chaos, ameliorating its brand identity and emotional appeal, and in turn its brand image. It is already happening through the commitment of the collective's collaborators in engaging the customers in an emotional way: as the recommendations are being applied, the brand emotional appeal is being transmitted to consumers. The Brand DNA serves as a creative trampoline for the collective to continue developing its brand. The application of the Brand DNA Process in the *favela* Santa Marta proves the flexibility, adaptability, and strength of such a methodology in creating an emotional appeal, which neuroscience demonstrates is decisive in triggering the emotional brain response – a consumer's identification and the amygdala preference – which, in its turn, is indispensable in creating a strong and virally emotional relationship between consumers and brands, that will guide purchasing decisions.

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